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1. General Descriptions

DOORS/101000518/3 contract titled; the project of “Oceanographic Sampling and Hydrodynamic Modeling in and around Yoroz(Trabzon), Fındıklı(Rize) and Hopa(Artvin) Harbors”. A hydrodynamic transport modelings was developed to model the coast in and around Yoroz(Trabzon), Fındıklı(Rize) and Hopa(Artvin) Harbors and Surroundings with the data to be obtained at the pilot points along the coast. In this context, first of all, oceanographic parameters were determined around these three ports. Before starting the measurements, the points to be measured were decided with the administration and monthly measurements were made at these points. Oceanographic parameters determined: Pressure, Temperature, Conductivity, Turbidity, Salinity, Sigma, current direction and intensity. Using the data obtained, a Hydrodynamic model based on the Princeton Ocean Model (POMSED) was developed and the flow velocity, direction and sediment distribution were simulated. The main features of the POMSED Model are as follows:

- Includes a second embedded moment turbulence submodel to provide vertical mixing coefficients. • It is a sigma coordinate model because the vertical coordinate scales with the depth of the water column.
- In horizontal gridding, it uses curvilinear orthogonal coordinates and the "Arakawa C" differencing method.
- The model has a free surface and a split time step. The external mode portion of the model is two-dimensional and uses a short time step depending on the CFL state and external wave velocity. Internal mode is three-dimensional and uses a long time step depending on the CFL condition and internal wave velocity.

As a result, the effect of sediment distribution to the determined ports (Yoroz (Trabzon), Fındıklı (Rize) and Hopa (Artvin) Ports) will be shown graphically and suggestions will be made about how long the ports should be cleaned.

1.1. Description and History of Hopa Port

Hopa Port is located at the eastern border of Eastern Black Sea, and 15 kilometers from Sarp Border Crossing which constitutes the border between CIS and Republic of Georgia.

Project design was completed in 1962 for the first time; the construction of the Port commenced in 1963, and the completed sections was brought into service in 1972. Operated under the title Hopa Port Authority, affiliated with Denizcilik Bankası T.A.O. (Maritime Bank), Trabzon Port Authority Directorate at first, and with partial ongoing distribution works, Hopa Port was transformed to independent Authority Directorate within the body of Trkiye Denizcilik İŐletmeleri A.Ő. General Directorate (Turkey Maritime Organization) in August 1986.

Continuing its operations under Trkiye Denizcilik İŐletmeleri A.Ő. Hopa Port Authority Directorate, Hopa Port was privatized on the date of June 17, 1997 pursuant to the resolution of Prime Ministry Privatization Administration High Board of Privatization published in the Official Gazette dated May 9, 1997 and numbered 22984 regarding the privatization by method of transferring the operating rights for a period of 30 years, and transferred to Park Denizcilik

Ve Hopa Liman İşletmeleri A.Ş. by Türkiye Denizcilik İşletmeleri A.Ş. effective by the date of June 27, 1997

Figure 1: Hopa port

Operating the Hopa Port, privatized in 1997, Hopa Port continues to contribute to the country's economy with loading, unloading, terminal, storage, pilotage, rescue and liquid filling facility operations. With its geographical location, Hopa Port is considered as the gate of Eastern Black Sea to the world.

By simplifying the arrival of cotton, shipped from Central Asia to the world, to Hopa Port; Park Denizcilik, with its investments, continues to provide opportunities for transportation to both domestic market and other countries specified by the buyer companies. With ongoing investment in this field, Hopa Port contributes to Eastern Black Sea substantially in economical aspects, and considered as the gate of the region to the world. Hopa Port is not only Turkey's, but also Black Sea's and Central Asia's one of the important ports with the advantages of its geographical location, capacity, broad hinterland, as well as easy access to inland and abroad.

Figure 2 : Breakwaters of Hopa port

BREAKWATERS

There are two breakwaters at Park Denizcilik ve Hopa Liman İşletmeleri.	LENGTH (m)
Primary Breakwater	2150
Secondary Breakwater	470
Entry Clearance	250

Table 1 : Properties of quays at Hopa port

QUAYS	LENGHT(m)	Draft
1-Ore and tank terminal dock	215 m	9,5 m
2-Ro-Ro dock	38 m	5,5 m
3-General cargo dock 1	190 m	10 m
4-General cargo dock 2	100 m	9,5 m
5-General cargo dock 3	198 m	9,5 m
6-General cargo dock 4	180 m	4 m
7-Fishermen's dock	120 m	4 m
8-Military dock	100 m	5 m
9-Grain dock(SILO)	200 m	9,5 m

2. Sampling Stations

2.1. Sampling stations of Hopa

Nine sampling stations were chosen to obtain seawater properties e.g. Temperature, salinity, and oxygen. Coordinates of sampling stations are given in Table 2.

Table 2 : Coordinates of sampling stations at Hopa

Hopa Port	Longitude	Latitude
H1	41.931440	41.408566
H2	41.398080	41.408112
H3	41.405283	41.414330
H4	41.413031	41.418135
H5	41.422720	41.426326
H6	41.430040	41.431314
H7	41.428179	41.439599
H8	41.419656	41.433824
H9	41.413700	41.429199

Figure 3: Sampling stations at Hopa

After measurements, topography of area was drawn and given in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Figure 4. Contour graph of Hopa topography

Figure 5.3-D graph of Hopa topography

Then results were plotted versus water depth. Monthly results were given between Figure 6 - Figure 13.

Figure 6 : Changes of Oxygen, salinity and temperature with depth in November at Hopa port

Figure 7: Changes of Oxygen, salinity and temperature with depth in January at Hopa port

Figure 8 : Changes of Oxygen, salinity and temperature with depth in February at Hopa port

Figure 9 : Changes of Oxygen, salinity and temperature with depth in March at Hopa port

Figure 10 : Changes of Oxygen, salinity and temperature with depth in April at Hopa port

Figure 11 : Changes of Oxygen, salinity and temperature with depth in May at Hopa port

Figure 12 : Changes of Oxygen, salinity and temperature with depth in June at Hopa port

Figure 13 : Changes of Oxygen, salinity and temperature with depth in July at Hopa port

3. Sampling stations of Fındıklı

Coordinates of sampling stations are given in Table 3.

Table 3 : Sampling stations of Fındıklı

FINDIKLI	Longitude	Latitude
F1	41.256703	41.118621
F2	41.261387	41.122299
F3	41.264625	41.124421
F4	41.267310	41.122037
F5	41.269774	41.127453
F6	41.274615	41.132126
F7	41.273298	41.137067
F8	41.265560	41.130983
F9	41.259175	41.126664

Figure 14. Sampling stations at Fındıklı

After measurements, topography of area was drawn and given in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Figure 15. Contour plot of Fındıklı Topography

Figure 16. 3-D plot of Fındıklı Topography

4. Sampling stations of Yoroz

Coordinates of sampling stations are given in Table 4.

Table 4 Sampling stations of Yoroz

YOROZ	ENLEM	BOYLAM
Y1	41.107455	39.423248
Y2	41.107985	39.426754
Y3	41.107760	39.430396
Y4	41.109164	39.434859
Y5	41.105882	39.434868
Y6	41.106918	39.439835
Y7	41.102887	39.438892
Y8	41.102430	39.433449
Y9	41.104018	39.428498

Figure 17. Sampling stations at Yoroz

Figure 18. CTD results measured in November 2021

Figure 19. CTD results measured in December 2021

Figure 20. CTD results measured in January 2022

Figure 21. CTD results measured in February 2022

Figure 22. CTD results measured in April 2022

Figure 23. CTD results measured in May 2022

Figure 24. CTD results measured in June 2021

Figure 25. CTD results measured in July 2022

3. Simulations:

3.1. Simulations at Fındıklı

To estimate distribution of sediments carried by Fındıklı river on Fındıklı Port, 8 wind directions (N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW) were taken in to account in simulations.

3.1.1. North wind direction

Figure 26: Simulation of surface current under N wind condition at Fındıklı

As seen from Figure 34 that sediment carried with current reaches the port entrance, there are considerable sediment accumulations at the mouth of port under this wind conditions.

3.1.2. Northeast wind direction

Figure 27: Simulation of surface current under NE wind condition at Fındıklı

Figure 34 that sediment carried with current reaches the port entrance, sediment accumulations have considerable effect on the filling of the fındıklı port.

3.1.3. East wind direction

Figure 28: Simulation of surface current under E wind condition at Fındıklı

Figure 28 shows that sediment carried with current reaches the port entrance, sediment accumulations have some effect on the filling of the findıklı port.

3.1.4. Southeast wind direction

Figure 29: Simulation of surface current under SE wind condition at Fındıklı

Figure 29 shows that sediment carried with current reaches the port entrance, sediment accumulations have some effect on the filling of the fındıklı port.

3.1.5. South wind direction

Figure 30: Simulation of surface current under S wind condition at Fındıklı

As seen from Figure 30 that sediment carried with current does not reach the port entrance, therefore, there is no sediment accumulations at the mouth of port under this wind conditions.

3.1.6. Southwest wind direction

Figure 31: Simulation of surface current under SW wind condition at Fındıklı

As seen from Figure 31 that sediment carried with current at the opposite direction of the port entrance, therefore, there is no sediment accumulations at the mouth of port under this wind conditions.

3.1.7. West wind direction

Figure 32: Simulation of surface current under W wind condition at Fındıklı

As seen from Figure 32 that sediment carried with current at away from the port entrance, therefore, there is no sediment accumulations at the mouth of port under this wind conditions.

3.1.8. Northwest wind direction

Figure 33: Simulation of surface current under W wind condition at Fındıklı

As seen from Figure 33 that sediment carried with current at away from the port entrance, therefore, there is no sediment accumulations at the mouth of port under this wind conditions.

3.2. Simulations at Hopa

In order to estimate the effect of sediments carried by Hopa river on Hopa Port, 4 wind directions (W,S,SW,NW) were used in simulations to show sediment distributions. Because, other wind directions carry sediments away from Hopa port and have no effect on filling of the port.

3.2.1. Northwest wind direction

Figure 34: Simulation of surface current under NW wind condition at Hopa

As seen from Figure 34 that sediment carried with current reaches the port entrance, but, since entrance of port faces the opposite way of current, there is no considerable sediment accumulations at the mouth of port under this wind conditions.

3.2.2. South wind direction

Figure 35: Simulation of surface current under S wind condition at Hopa

As seen from Figure 35 that sediment carried with current reaches the port entrance, but, since entrance of port faces the opposite way of current and wind direction the SW, there is no considerable sediment accumulations at the mouth of port under this wind conditions.

3.2.3. South West wind direction

Figure 36: Simulation of surface current under SW wind condition at Hopa

Figure 36 shows that sediment carried with current reaches the port entrance, there are some accumulations on the entrance of port. These accumulations fill the port entrance about 2.5 cm each year.

3.2.4. West wind direction

Figure 37: Simulation of surface current under SW wind condition at Hopa

Figure 37 shows that sediment carried with current reaches the port entrance, there are some accumulations on the entrance of port. But, this is not enough to take into consideration.

3.3. Simulations at Yoroç

As seen from Figure 38, Yoroç promontory has two sides and mouth of river on the opposite side of port entrance . In order to estimate the effect of sediments carried by Hopa river on Hopa Port, 6 wind directions (N,S,SW,NW,E,SE) were used in simulations to show sediment distributions.

Figure 38. View of Yoroç promontory from Google Earth

3.3.1. North wind direction

Figure 39: Simulation of surface current under N wind condition at Yoroz promontory

Figure 39 shows that sediment carried with current reaches the port entrance, there are some accumulations on the entrance of port. But, this is not enough to take into consideration.

3.3.2. East wind direction

Figure 40: Simulation of surface current under E wind condition at Yozgat promontory

Figure 40 shows that sediment carried with current does not reach the port entrance, therefore, there is no accumulations on the entrance of port under this wind condition.

3.3.3. Southeast wind direction

Figure 41: Simulation of surface current under SE wind condition at Yoroz promontory

Figure 41 shows that sediment carried with current does not reach the port entrance, therefore, there is no accumulations on the entrance of port under this wind condition.

3.3.4. South wind direction

Figure 42: Simulation of surface current under S wind condition at Yoroz promontory

Figure 42 shows that sediment carried with current does not reach the port entrance, therefore, there is no accumulations on the entrance of port under this wind condition.

3.3.5. Southwest wind direction

Figure 43: Simulation of surface current under SW wind condition at Yoroz promontory

Figure 43 shows that sediment carried with current does not reach the port entrance, therefore, there is no accumulations on the entrance of port under this wind condition.

3.3.6. West wind direction

Figure 44: Simulation of surface current under W wind condition at Yoroz promontory

Figure 44 shows that sediment carried with current reaches the port entrance, But, there are small amount of accumulations on the entrance of port under this wind condition at Yoroz promontory.

3.3.7. Northwest wind direction

Figure 45: Simulation of surface current under NW wind condition at Yoroz promontory

Figure 45 shows that sediment carried with current reaches the port entrance, But, there are small amount of accumulations on the entrance of port under this wind condition at Yoroz promontory.

6. Discussions

In this project of “Oceanographic Sampling and Hydrodynamic Modeling in and around Yoro(Trabzon), Fındıklı(Rize) and Hopa(Artvin) Harbors”, a hydrodynamic transport modeling was developed to model the coast in and around Yoro(Trabzon), Fındıklı(Rize) and Hopa(Artvin) Harbors and Surroundings with the data to be obtained at the selected points along the coast. In this context, first of all, oceanographic parameters (temperature, salinity, oxygen, and currents) were determined around these three ports.

Then, simulations were done by using all main wind directions (N,NE,W,NW,S,SW,SE,E,) at Yoro, Fındıklı and Hopa ports. Only significant current situations which carries sediment to ports were taken into account and given in this report.

If Hopa port is concern, it can be seen that wind directions S,SW,W and NW carried sediment to port. None of this transportation showed significant effect on filling the port with sediment. This is because of two reasons: First one is the distance between port and river mouth, and second one is the location of Hopa port entrance.

Simulations at Fındıklı port illustrated that N, NE, E and SE wind directions push sediment to Fındıklı port. Results of simulations showed that sediment filling at Fındıklı port reaches significant height after 25 to 30 years. This results indicates that Fındıklı port needs to be emptied after every 25 to 30 years.

Yoro simulations indicates that N, SW, W and NW wind directions can carry sediment to Yoro port. But, since there is a promontory between river mouth and Yoro port. Sediment reached the port had no significant effect on filling of port.

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